

UNVEILING CLARITY: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON THE ACCESSIBILITY OF LEGAL LANGUAGE FOR LAW STUDENTS IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The complex nature of Legal language is a significant aspect that influences law students to accomplish their academic tasks. The aim of the paper is to improve the comprehensibility and to save the time of Law students of Pakistan. For this, data is gathered from 250 students from five major universities of Pakistan through a test. Two test (1 & 2) were designed which were comprised of five criminal statutes with both versions, original and simplified to measure the comprehension level of law students. After reading each statement regarding criminal statutes, the respondents were supposed to answer the questions followed by each statute. These questions were true/false and short questions. Each question carried equal marks. The instructions were also given to the students in order to mention the starting and ending time of the test. After attempting the test 1, the same students were given 'test two' in simplified version. Data is analyzed through SPSS by using descriptive and ANOVA tests. The result revealed the significant difference between both tests in terms of enhancement of comprehensibility and efficiency in Pakistani academic legal settings.

Keywords: *Clarity, Comprehension, Legal Language, Plain English Principles, Time Saving*

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1. Introduction

Legal language is considered a discrete variety of English language. "For the masses, the legal language is so difficult to comprehend due to its particular linguistic features" (Tiersma, 1999). Its complex features are considered as a heritage of different prevailing languages e.g. Latin, French, Italian, and Norman etc. "It differs from ordinary language not in vocabulary, but also in morphology, syntax, semantics and other linguistic features" (Wydick, 2005b, p.10). These features make legal writing poor that is cluttered, wordy, indirect, and uses unnecessary technical words or phrases" (Butler, 2013, p. 32). The traditional style of legal writing has been labeled as reader-unfriendly (Butler, 2013, p. 32).

The intricacy of legal language acts a significant obstacle for Pakistani academic legal settings; makes an impact on law students' comprehension abilities, clarity and time consumption. In our society, the young lawyers have to face the problems in terms of comprehension, clarity, and dealing with legal matters. In this regard, the major cause is the flawed academic system because the colleges/universities offering law degrees do not provide them sufficient knowledge to be skillful. Traditional syllabi are taught to them with intricate language as well bad practices are made in those institutes which are transmitted to the future lawyers. Yet outdated legacy of colonial powers regarding laws and legal system have been working in educational system of Pakistan. It creates a lacunae between the bookish knowledge and practices. These outdated syllabi do not provide the clarity and understanding of the legal texts. For this, they have to do internship after getting law degree. This internship period under any senior lawyer may extend from 5 to 10 years to be an eminent part of legal professional bodies. In this long period, they learn how to be familiar with legal texts, drafting and legal proceedings that becomes the cause of wastage of time, which breeds further issues for the young lawyers. So, the laws are required to be comprehensible for the law students.

As a reaction to the complex nature of legal language, *the plain English Movement* was developed around the globe. The primary purpose of the plain language is to stress on making sense of obscure language or sentence structure. The drafters of plain language consider the reader's needs and accessibility regarding quick and clear understanding of the documents including layout, design, format, and the 'plainness' of the words used (Abrahams, 2003).

This study aims to address this issue by measuring the linguistic adequacy of law students concerning the comprehension level and required time of comprehending statutes in original and simplified versions so that the problems regarding the complexity of legal language and consequently recommendations be given to improve comprehension and to save time.

Through this investigation, I am intended to address the problem from a unique angle:

Complex legal statutes require more time for comprehension than that of legal texts produced in plain English.

Taking this as a hypothesis, I will investigate:

Whether statutes written in plain English save law students' time in accomplishing academic legal tasks?

If, the hypothesis is proved, the researchers will recommend the popularization of *Plain English Movement* in Pakistani academic legal settings.

In this regard, following research have been generated:

1. Out of the two versions of legal English (original & simplified), which one is better in terms of academic achievements?

1.1. Subsidiary Questions

1. How much time is spent in comprehending statutes written in complex legal language?
2. How much time is spent in comprehending statutes written in plain language?
3. What is the difference of time with reference to reading both versions?
4. To what extent, comprehension is adequate with reference to statutes produced in complex legal language?
5. To what extent, comprehension is adequate with reference to statutes produced in plain English?

2. Literature Review

Domselaar (2022) took the initiative by implementing the plain language principles on court ruling of Dutch to make its intelligible for the citizens and law practitioners. He analyzed and evaluated the simplified legal language employed by court rulings and found it relevant to civic friendly. On the other hand, Mahbuba (2023) explored the linguistics features involved in complexity of legal language which act as barrier to understand it and significance of Plain English to make it reader friendly for non-lawyers and policy makers of Uzbekistan. Similarly, Raaj (2021) emphasized on significance and requirement of plain English movement for all over the globe to transform their legal documents for legal consumers and common man. He also highlighted the criticism passed and provided the solutions in relation to the issues raised by the implementation of plain English principles. Likewise, Lin, Afzaal & Aldayel (2023) explored the efficacy of plain language by making comparison between original and simplified company law corpora in terms of syntactic complexity. Significant statistical difference was observed between two big datasets gathered from three locations.

On the other hand, Manoor & Li (2019) employed the technique of *Plain English Movement*, ‘summarization’, to bring the clarity of legal contracts. They found its efficacy but emphasized on the need of more plain English techniques, legal jargons and style to make the clear understanding of contracts in their particular context for the audiences. Likewise, Riera (2015) executed a research to make the comparison between two versions of UK acts of parliament to check the Plain Principles applied in terms of modern style. Also, Rubab (2018) explored the effects of text simplification to speed up Justice in Pakistan.

Contrarily, Zodi (2019) executed a research to investigate the style to comprehend the legal language by offering a pragmatic framework. Whereas, Evans (2020) focused on the implementation of plain English principles on health literacy journal writing for health high graduates to train the staff and to make familiar with health information to the public. Tariq (2021) took an initiative to make the comprehensibility of Pakistani business laws for the public by making the implementation of principles of text simplification. Riganti & McKinnon (2023) conducted a research on the medical language by simplifying its medical terms to make accessible for patients. Rubab (2019), (2020) & (2022) has explored the impact of simplifying legal texts; in form of civil statutes, and criminal judicial judgements, on law discourse community with reference to comprehensibility and time saving to expedite the justice in Pakistan. As well, Rubab (2025) has explored the perceptions of legal community to simplify the legal language. Multiple researches have been executed in different domains across the globe. In the current study, the researchers have been fulfilling the gap by measuring the implementation of text simplification principles on criminal statutory laws for Pakistani law students in order to improve their comprehensibility and time saving.

3. Methodology

For quantitative analysis, the comprehension level of law students with reference to statutes in both versions; original and simplified are considered. Data was gathered from following five universities of Pakistan: The Bahauddin Zakariya University, Punjab University, Peshawar University, Karachi University and Baluchistan University. The test was conducted among 250 students; fifty students from each university. Out of which, 231 respondents attempted the tests and returned it to the researchers. In order to investigate the comprehension level of law students, two tests (test 1& test 2) were given to the students. Test 1 was comprised of statutes in original complex language, while in test two the statutes in simplified language were included. Both tests were comprised of five statements. After reading each statement regarding criminal statutes, the respondents were supposed to answer the questions followed by each statute. These questions were true/false and short questions. Each question carried equal marks. The instructions were given to the students in order to mention the starting and ending time of the test. After attempting the

test 1, the same students were given ‘test two’. For statistical analysis, SPSS was applied to analyze the data.

3.1. Analysis of Criminal Statutes

It deals with findings related to statutes. These findings demonstrate students’ comprehension, time spent and difference of time with reference to both versions of statutes. Analysis in relation to statutes is given below:

3.2. Law Students’ Comprehension with Reference to Original Statutes

A total number of research participants were 250 law students, out of which 231 attempted the test. Fifty students responded from Bahauddin Zakariya University by obtaining average marks 4.9600 with standard deviation 1.66. Minimum and maximum scores obtained by the students were 2.00 and 8.50 respectively. Similarly, forty seven students attempted the test from Punjab University by securing average marks 5.38 with standard deviation 1.37. Minimum and maximum scores in this case were 3.00 and 8.00 respectively. However, from Peshawar University, 45 students attempted the test who secured 6.48 average marks with standard deviation 1.19. In this regard, the minimum score was 3.00 and maximum was 8.00. Likewise, 45 students from Karachi University secured 5.42 average marks with standard deviation 1.13. The minimum and maximum marks obtained by the students were 3.00 and 7.00 respectively. On the other hand, 44 students appeared from Baluchistan University; mean and standard deviation were 4.09 and 1.42 respectively with minimum score 1.00 and maximum score 7.00.

Overall, the students who attempted the test secured average 5.26 marks with standard deviation 1.56. Minimum and maximum scores were 1.00 and 8.50. (See table: 1.1)

Table 1.1 *Descriptive Statistics: Marks Regarding Comprehension of Original Statutes*

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum	
Bahauddin Zakariya University	50	4.9600	1.66807	.23590	2.00	8.50	
Punjab University	47	5.3830	1.37609	.20072	3.00	8.00	
Peshawar University	45	6.4889	1.19891	.17872	3.00	8.00	
Karachi University	45	5.4222	1.13796	.16964	3.00	7.00	

Baluchistan University	44	4.0909	1.42760	.21522	1.00	7.00
Total	231	5.2684	1.56841	.10319	1.00	8.50

The comprehension ability among the students of different universities was found significantly different. Table ANOVA 1.2 shows F-value 17.66 with P-value 0.000. It means the average marks obtained by the students of different universities are significantly different.

Table 1.2 ANOVA: Marks Regarding Comprehension of Original Statutes

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	134.474	4	33.619	17.616	.000
Within Groups	431.305	226	1.908		
Total	565.779	230			

3.3. Law Students' Comprehension with Reference to Simplified Statutes

Out of total 250 research participants, 231 students participated in the test. Fifty students from Bahauddin Zakariya University took part in the test and secured average marks 7.22 with standard deviation 1.09. Minimum scores achieved by the students were 5.00 and maximum 9.00 respectively. Similarly, forty seven students attempted the test from Punjab University by securing average marks 7.18 with standard deviation 1.49. Minimum and maximum scores in this regard were 3.00 and 9.50 respectively. On the other hand, 45 law students participated from Peshawar University securing 7.91 average marks with standard deviation 1.01. Minimum and maximum scores were 5.00 and 10.00 respectively. Similarly, 45 law students from Karachi University secured 6.70 average marks with standard deviation 1.26. Minimum and maximum marks obtained by the students were 4.00 and 9.00 respectively. On the other hand, 44 law students appeared in the test from Baluchistan University. Mean and standard deviation was 6.45 and 2.55 respectively with minimum score 3.00 and maximum score 14.70.

Overall, out of 231 law students, who attempted the test, secured average 7.09 marks with standard deviation 1.634. Minimum and maximum scores obtained by the students were 3.00 and 14.70 as indicated in table 1.3.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.1.3 Descriptive: Marks Regarding Comprehension of Simplified Statutes

N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
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Bahauddin Zakariya University	50	7.2200	1.09339	.15463	5.00	9.00
Punjab University Peshawar	47	7.1809	1.49428	.21796	3.00	9.50
Peshawar University	45	7.9111	1.01852	.15183	5.00	10.00
Karachi University	45	6.7000	1.26311	.18829	4.00	9.00
Balochistan University	44	6.4545	2.55575	.38529	3.00	14.70
Total	231	7.0996	1.63411	.10752	3.00	14.70

The comprehension ability regarding simplified statutes among the students of different universities was found significantly different. Table ANOVA 1.4 shows F-value 5.687 with P-value 0.000. It reflects that the students of different universities are showing highly significant different average marks.

Table 1.4 ANOVA: Marks Regarding Comprehension of Simplified Statutes

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	56.164	4	14.041	5.687	.000
Within Groups	558.006	226	2.469		
Total	614.170	230			

3.4. Law Students' Time Spent in Comprehending Original Statutes

As it is mentioned earlier, out of a total number of 250 students, 231 students participated in the test. With reference to measuring time while attempting the test, from Bahauddin Zakariya University, fifty students appeared in the test spending average time 15.42 with standard deviation 2.83. Minimum time spent was 10.00 minutes and maximum 21.00 minutes. Similarly, forty seven students took the test from Punjab University by taking average time 18.76 with standard deviation 4.16. Minimum and maximum time spent in this regard was 8.00 and 27.00 respectively. Conversely, 45 law students from Peshawar University took part consuming 18.488 minutes average with standard deviation 2.84. Minimum and maximum time spent was 13.00 and 23.00 minutes respectively. Similarly, 45 students from Karachi University took 15.488 minutes average with 4.25 standard deviation. Minimum and maximum time spent by the students was 7.00 and 25.00 minutes respectively. On the other hand, 44 students participated from Baluchistan University consuming 21.659 minutes average with standard deviation 3.79. Minimum and maximum time spent was 15.00 and 35.00 minutes respectively.

Overall, out of 231 law students, who attempted the test, took average 17.90 minutes with standard deviation 4.27. Minimum and maximum time taken was 7.00 and 35.00 as indicated in table 1.5.

Table 1.5 *Descriptive: Time Spent in Comprehending Original Statutes*

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Bahauddin Zakariya University	50	15.4200	2.84347	.40213	10.00	21.00
Punjab University	47	18.7660	4.16618	.60770	8.00	27.00
Peshawar University	45	18.4889	2.84942	.42477	13.00	23.00
Karachi University	45	15.4889	4.25132	.63375	7.00	25.00
Balochistan University	44	21.6591	3.79071	.57147	15.00	35.00
Total	231	17.9004	4.27669	.28139	7.00	35.00

The time spent in comprehending the original statutes among the students of different universities was found significantly different. Table ANOVA 1.6 shows F-value 23.662 with P-value 0.00. It shows the time taken in comprehending the statutes by the students of different universities is significantly different.

Table 1.6 *ANOVA: Time Spent in Comprehending Original Statutes*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1241.729	4	310.432	23.662	.000
Within Groups	2964.981	226	13.119		
Total	4206.710	230			

3.5. Law Students' Time Spent in Comprehending Simplified Statutes

As it is previously mentioned, out of a total number of 250 research participants, 231 students participated in the test. With reference to measuring the time while attempting the test pertaining to simplified statutes, from Bahauddin Zakariya University, fifty students appeared in the test who consumed average time 7.68 with standard deviation 1.707. Minimum time spent was 5.00 minutes and maximum 10.00 minutes. Similarly, forty seven students took the test from Punjab University by taking average time 8.76 with standard deviation 1.855. Minimum and maximum time spent in this regard was 3.00 and 13.00 respectively. Conversely, 45 law students from Peshawar University took part consuming 8.93 minutes average with standard deviation 1.572. Minimum and maximum time spent was 6.00 and 13.00 minutes respectively. Similarly, 45 students from Karachi University took 8.066 minutes average with 3.53 standard deviation. Minimum and maximum time spent by the students was 3.00 and 20.00 minutes respectively. On the

other hand, 44 law students participated from Baluchistan University consuming 14.159 minutes average with standard deviation 2.31. Minimum and maximum time spent was 10.00 and 18.00 minutes respectively.

Consequently, the students who attempted the test took average 9.45 minutes with standard deviation 3.22. Minimum and maximum time taken by the law students was 3.00 and 20.00 as indicated in table 1.7.

Table 1.7 Descriptives: Time Spent in Comprehending Simplified Statutes

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Bahauddin Zakariya University	50	7.6800	1.70761	.24149	5.00	10.00
Punjab University	47	8.7660	1.85581	.27070	3.00	13.00
Peshawar University	45	8.9333	1.57249	.23441	6.00	13.00
Karachi University	45	8.0667	3.35342	.49990	3.00	20.00
Balochistan University	44	14.1591	2.31218	.34857	10.00	18.00
Total	231	9.4545	3.22171	.21197	3.00	20.00

The time spent in comprehending the simplified statutes among the students of different universities was found significantly different. Analysis of Variance is used to determine the statistical difference between the means of independent groups as presented in table 1.8. It shows F-value 62.362 with P-value 0.00 reflecting the significant difference of the time required in comprehending the statutes by the students of different universities.

Table 1.8 ANOVA: Time Spent in Comprehending Simplified Statutes

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1252.481	4	313.120	62.360	.000
Within Groups	1134.792	226	5.021		
Total	2387.273	230			

3.6. Difference of Time with reference to Original and Simplified Statutes

With reference to the difference of time that is spent on reading original and simplified statutes, descriptive statistics is applied to provide the description of variables. It takes account of mode, median, standard deviation, standard error, minimum and maximum value. In this regard, the students of Bahauddin Zakariya University took 7.74 minutes average with standard deviation 3.008. Minimum time spent was 1.00 minutes and maximum 15.00 minutes respectively. Similarly, the students of Punjab University indicated average time difference 10.00 minutes with standard deviation 3.72. In this case, minimum and maximum difference of time was 3.00 and 19.00 minutes respectively.

Conversely, the students of Peshawar University reflected average time difference 9.55 minutes with standard deviation 2.70. Minimum and maximum time spent was 2.00 and 15.00 minutes respectively. Similarly, students from Karachi University indicated average time difference 7.42 minutes with standard deviation 3.77. Minimum and maximum time difference was 0.00 and 15.00 minutes respectively. On the other hand, the results of Balochistan University show that the mean time difference was 7.5 minutes with standard deviation 4.11. Minimum and maximum time spent was 0.00 and 25.00 minutes respectively.

Overall, the results indicate the average time difference is 8.44 minutes with standard deviation 3.63. Minimum and maximum time taken is 0.00 and 25.00 as shown in table 1.9.

Table 1.9

Descriptive Time Difference in Comprehending Original & Simplified Statutes

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Bahauddin Zakariya University	50	7.7400	3.00890	.42552	1.00	15.00
Punjab University	47	10.0000	3.72419	.54323	3.00	19.00
Peshawar University	45	9.5556	2.70148	.40271	2.00	15.00
Karachi University	45	7.4222	3.77485	.56272	.00	15.00
Balochistan University	44	7.5000	4.11181	.61988	.00	25.00
Total	231	8.4459	3.63382	.23909	.00	25.00

The difference of time in comprehending both versions of statutes among the students of different universities was found significantly different. Table ANOVA 1.10 indicates F-value 5.74 with P-value 0.00. It shows that the time required in comprehending the statutes by the students of different universities is significantly different.

Table 1.10

ANOVA:

Time Difference in Comprehending Original & Simplified Statutes

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	280.365	4	70.091	5.746	.000
Within Groups	2756.709	226	12.198		
Total	3037.074	230			

3.7. Overall Findings

The combined analysis of original and simplified law marks of statutes revealed that total 231 students participated in the test. With reference to original statutes, the average marks secured by the students are 5.26 with standard deviation 1.56, while regarding simplified statutes; the average marks obtained by the students are 7.09 with standard deviation 1.63 as shown in table 1.11.

Table 1.1 *Paired*
Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1				
Marks Regarding Comprehension of Original Statutes	5.2684	231	1.56841	.10319
Marks Regarding Comprehension of Simplified Statutes	7.0996	231	1.63411	.10752

It is evident from the table 1.12 reflecting a positive correlation in the marks secured for both types of problems. The positive correlation is observed by the students is 0.620 that is highly significant with p value=0.00.

Table 1.32
Paired Samples Correlations

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1			
Marks Regarding Original Statutes & Marks Regarding Simplified Statutes	231	.620	.000

A paired T-Test is applied, the mean difference between the marks secured by the students is -1.83 with standard deviation 1.39. The value of t-statistics obtained was -19.92 with p-value 0.00 which is again highly significant as mentioned in table: 1.13. It reflects the significant difference among the students of different universities while attempting the test with reference to comprehension of original and simplified versions of the text.

Table 1.43

Paired Samples Test

Pair	Marks of Original Statutes – Marks of Simplified Statutes	Paired Differences			t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean			
1		1.83117	1.39673	0.9190	-19.926	230	.000

The combined analysis of both versions of statutes is presented in the under given tables. Regarding original version of the statutes, the average time taken by the students is 1.90 minutes with standard deviation 4.26, while regarding simplified statutes the average time spent by the students is 9.45 minutes with standard deviation 3.22 as mentioned in the table: 1.14.

Table 1.14
Paired Samples Statistics

Pair	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1 Time Spent in Comprehending Original Statutes-	17.9004	231	4.27669	.28139
Time Spent in Comprehending Simplified statutes	9.4545	231	3.22171	.21197

The table 1.15 shows a positive correlation in the time taken for both types of problems. Positive correlation by the students is 0.561, that is highly significant with p value=0.00.

Table 1.15
Paired Samples Correlations

Pair	N	Correlation	Sig.
1 Time Spent in Original Statutes & Time Spent in Simplified Statutes	231	.561	.000

A paired T-Test is applied, the mean difference between the times consumed by the students is 8.44 minutes with standard deviation 3.66. The value of T-statistics obtained was 35.25 with p-value 0.00 which is again highly significant. It indicates the significant difference with reference to time taken by the students of different universities while attempting the test with reference to original and simplified versions of the statutes as presented in table 1.16.

Table 1.16
Paired Samples Test for Original Law Time of Statutes - Simplified Law Time of Statutes

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
			Std. Error	Mean		Std. Error	Mean
Pair 1	8.44589	3.63382	.23909	35.325	230		.000

4. Conclusion

In the undertaken study, the findings related to the linguistic adequacy level of law students of different universities of Pakistan regarding statutes have been reported. First, in the context of original statutes, the students secured average 5.26 score with standard deviation 1.56, whereas in case of simplified statutes, the students scored average 7.09 marks with standard deviation 1.63. That shows a positive correlation between the original and simplified law marks of the students. Second, with reference to consumption of time while comprehending the original statutes, the students took average 1.90 minutes with standard deviation 4.26, whereas regarding simplified statutes; the students took 9.45 minutes with standard deviation 3. That shows a positive correlation in consumption of time while reading both versions of statutes. Third, by applying T-test, the mean difference between the times consumed by the students is 8.44 minutes with standard deviation. The value of T- statistics obtained was 35.25 with p-value 0.00 which is highly significant. It indicates a significant difference with reference to consumption of time while reading original and simplified versions of the statutes.

On the whole, it is concluded that the students secured more marks while comprehending the simplified statutes as compared to the original statutes. It reflects the students feel difficulty in comprehending the original legal text. As well, the students take more time while reading the original statutes as compared to the simplified statutes. A significant time difference is calculated by comparing both versions of statutes. It shows that the simplified versions of the legal texts should be encouraged in order to get better understanding and time saving.

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